

1, 3, 4-Oxadiazoles : Part III. Mannich Bases Derived from 5-(*o*-) Hydroxyphenyl-1, 3, 4-Oxadiazol-2-thione

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A number of 3-substituted aminomethyl-5-(*o*-)hydroxyphenyl-1, 3, 4-oxadiazol-2-thiones have been prepared by the application of Mannich reaction. The site of the substituent in the Mannich bases has been confirmed by stepwise synthesis, interconversions and spectral comparison. A few of the Mannich bases were evaluated as anticonvulsants.

THE hypoglycemic¹, antitubercular², antiviral³, antifungal⁴, and carcinostatic⁶ properties exhibited by cyclic compounds such as oxadiazoles, thiadiazoles and mercaptotriazoles have made them important chemotherapeutic agents. Pharmacological screening of some 5-substituted-1, 3, 4-oxadiazol-2-ones (I) have shown that they possess antimycobacterial activity¹. This gave a basis for a systematic study of oxadiazoles as they themselves may show pharmacodynamic properties. 5-substituted oxadiazol-2-ones (I) were converted into 3-substituted aminomethyl-5-substituted-1, 3, 4-oxadiazol-2-ones (II) by the application of Mannich reaction and were found to be highly active against mycobacterium tuberculosis in animals and men.⁶

gave the parent compound (III). The IR spectra of the Mannich bases revealed the presence of C = S bands as sharp and strong peaks in the region 1050-1090 cm⁻¹.

Synthesis :

All the m.p.s. are uncorrected.

5-(*o*-)Hydroxyphenyl-1, 3, 4-oxadiazol-2-thione : It was prepared by following the method of Young and Wood⁷ in 60% yield, m.p. 135°.

3-(*p*-) Hydroxyphenylaminomethyl-5(*o*-) hydroxyphenyl-1, 3, 4-oxadiazol-2-thione : To a cooled mixture of compound (III) (0.2g., 0.001 mole) and formal-

A comparative study of (II) with 5-substituted-1, 3, 4-oxadiazol-2-thiones (III) revealed that the latter are less active and toxic but more stable. To improve the activity, some new groups were introduced by the Mannich reaction into (III). The key intermediate, 5-(*o*-) hydroxyphenyl-1, 3, 4-oxadiazol-2-thione was prepared by the method of Young and Wood,⁷ and was subjected to Mannich reaction^{8,9} by condensing it in ethanolic medium with formaldehyde and various aromatic, and heterocyclic amines which gave 3-substituted aminomethyl-5-(*o*-) hydroxyphenyl-1, 3, 4-oxadiazol-2 thiones (IV). The Mannich bases on hydrolysis with 10% hydrochloric acid

gave the parent compound (III). The IR spectra of the Mannich bases revealed the presence of C = S bands as sharp and strong peaks in the region 1050-1090 cm⁻¹.
delyde (0.1g., 40%), an ethanolic solution of *p*-aminophenol (0.11g., 0.001 mole) was added dropwise and left in a refrigerator for two days. A white solid was obtained which was filtered and washed with ethanol. Product on crystallisation with ethanol afforded white needle shaped crystals, yield 60%, m.p. 155°. (Found : N, 13.5; C₁₅H₁₃N₃O₃S requires N, 13.33%).

3-(*p*-) Chlorophenylaminomethyl-5-(*o*-) hydroxyphenyl-1, 3, 4-oxadiazol-2-thione : To a mixture of ethanolic solution of 5-(*o*-) hydroxy phenyl-1, 3, 4-oxadiazol-2-thione (0.2g., 0.001 mole) and formaldehyde (0.1g., 40%), an ethanolic solution of *p*-chloroaniline

TABLE I. 3-ARYLAMINOMETHYL-5-(*o*-)HYDROXYPHENYL-1, 3, 4-OXADIAZOL-2-THIONE

S. No.	R	M.P. °C	Molecular formula	N(%)	
				Found	Calcd.
1.	Phenyl	145	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂ S	13.9	14.04
2.	<i>o</i> -Toyl	145	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ S	13.6	13.41
3.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	158	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ S	13.3	13.41
4.	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	115	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₃ S	13.1	12.75
5.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	125	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₃ S	12.8	12.75
6.	<i>o</i> -Phenetyl	135	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₃ S	12.5	12.24
7.	<i>p</i> -Phenetyl	100	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₃ S	12.1	12.24
8.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	160	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ BrN ₃ O ₂ S	11.4	11.11
9.	<i>p</i> -Acetylphenyl	200	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₃ S	12.5	12.31
10.	<i>p</i> -(<i>n</i> -)Butylcarboxylatephenyl	180	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₄ S	10.6	10.52
11.	<i>p</i> -Isobutylcarboxylatephenyl	188	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₄ S	10.7	10.52
12.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	200	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₄ S	16.3	16.22
13.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	210	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₄ S	16.5	16.22
14.	<i>m</i> -Carboxylphenyl	205	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₄ S	12.4	12.24
15.	<i>p</i> -Carboxylphenyl	212	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₄ S	12.5	12.24
16.	3-Hydroxy-4-sodium-carboxylatephenyl	220d	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₃ O ₆ SNa	11.3	11.02
17.	<i>p</i> -Dimethylaminophenyl	205d	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ S	16.5	16.37

d = Decompose

(0.13g., 0.001 mole) was added slowly with swirling. The reaction mixture was left in a refrigerator for 1 hr, when a white solid was obtained which was filtered, washed with ethanol and crystallisation from aqueous ethanol gave white shining needles. Yield 65%, m.p. 162°. (Found: N, 12.56%. C₁₅H₁₂ClN₃O₂S requires N, 12.66%)

Other compounds in this series were prepared in the same way and are presented along with relevant data in Table 1.

Anticonvulsant activity: Anticonvulsant activity of 3,5-disubstituted-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thiones was determined at a dose of 100 mg/kg. i.p. against pentylene-tetrazol induced seizures.^{10,11} Only a few oxadiazoles (No. 11, 12, 13 and 15—20% and compound 10—50% exhibited low anti-convulsant activity where maximum protection of 60% was observed with 3-(*p*-) chlorophenylaminomethyl 5-(*o*-) hydroxyphenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione. Administration of these compounds failed to protect pentylene tetrazol treated animals against death since 40-100% mortality was observed during 24 hrs period.

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